

Emerging complexity in the denitrification regulatory network of *Bradyrhizobium japonicum*

Mariía J. Torres, Emilio Bueno, Socorro Mesa, Eulogio J. Bedmar and María J. Delgado¹

Departamento de Microbiología del Suelo y Sistemas Simbióticos, Estación Experimental del Zaidín, CSIC, P.O. Box 419, 18080 Granada, Spain

¹To whom correspondence should be addressed (email mdelgado@eez.csic.es).

Abstract

Bradyrhizobium japonicum is a Gram-negative soil bacterium symbiotically associated with soya bean plants, which is also able to denitrify under free-living and symbiotic conditions. In *B. japonicum*, the *napEDABC*, *nirK*, *norCBQD* and *nosRZDYFLX* genes which encode reductases for nitrate, nitrite, nitric oxide and nitrous oxide respectively are required for denitrification. Similar to many other denitrifiers, expression of denitrification genes in *B. japonicum* requires both oxygen limitation and the presence of nitrate or a derived nitrogen oxide. In *B. japonicum*, a sophisticated regulatory network consisting of two linked regulatory cascades coordinates the expression of genes required for microaerobic respiration (the FixLJ/FixK₂ cascade) and for nitrogen fixation (the RegSR/NifA cascade). The involvement of the FixLJ/FixK₂ regulatory cascade in the microaerobic induction of the denitrification genes is well established. In addition, the FNR (fumarase and nitrate reduction regulator)/CRP(cAMP receptor protein)-type regulator NnrR expands the FixLJ/FixK₂ regulatory cascade by an additional control level. A role for NifA is suggested in this process by recent experiments which have shown that it is required for full expression of denitrification genes in *B. japonicum*. The present review summarizes the current understanding of the regulatory network of denitrification in *B. japonicum*.

Keywords: *Bradyrhizobium japonicum*, FixK₂, gene regulation, NifA, NorC, RegSR.

Abbreviations used: CRP, cAMP receptor protein; FNR, fumarase and nitrate reduction regulator; Nap, periplasmic nitrate reductase; NirK, copper-containing nitrite reductase; UQ, ubiquinone; YEM, yeast extract/mannitol.

Introduction

Rhizobia are Gram-negative nitrogen-fixing bacteria which establish symbiotic associations with legume plants leading to the formation of so-called nodules on legume roots and on the stems of some aquatic legumes. After invasion of the plant cells via a complex signalling pathway between bacteria and plant, rhizobia stop dividing and undergo differentiation into nitrogen-fixing bacteroids. In recent years, it has emerged that many rhizobia species have genes that encode enzymes required for some, or all, of the four reductase reactions for denitrification [1]. Although the ability to denitrify may enhance rhizobia survival and growth capability in anaerobic soils, only *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* and *Azorhizobium caulinodans* have been shown to grow under oxygen-limiting conditions, with nitrate, through the denitrification pathway. The soya bean symbiont *B. japonicum* is the only rhizobium species that has been identified as being able to denitrify under both free-living and symbiotic conditions. In *B. japonicum*, denitrification is dependent on the *napEDABC*, *nirK*, *norCBQD* and *nosRZDYFLX* genes that encode Nap (periplasmic nitrate reductase), NirK (copper-containing nitrite reductase), cNor (c-type nitric oxide reductase) and Nos (nitrous oxide reductase) enzymes respectively [2]. In *B. japonicum*, cytochrome *c₅₅₀*, encoded by *cycA*, is involved in electron transfer to NirK. This is shown by the inability of a *cycA* mutant to consume nitrite and, consequently, to grow under denitrifying conditions with nitrate or nitrite as the final electron acceptor [3]. It has been proposed that the *cycS* gene of *B. japonicum*, a gene which encodes a soluble cytochrome *c₆* of approx. 9 kDa, has a role in denitrification, although the precise biochemical function of CycS is currently not known [4]. Neither azurin- nor pseudoazurin-like copper proteins have been annotated in the genome sequence of *B. japonicum* (<http://www.kazusa.jp/rhizobase/>).

Similar to many other denitrifiers, expression of denitrification genes in *B. japonicum* requires both oxygen limitation and the presence of nitrate or a derived nitrogen oxide [2]. In *B. japonicum*, a sophisticated regulatory network, consisting of two linked regulatory cascades, co-ordinates the expression of genes required for microaerobic respiration (the FixLJ/FixK₂ cascade) and for nitrogen fixation (the RegSR/NifA cascade). In these two cascades, different oxygen-sensing mechanisms are responsible for a stepwise activation of downstream events [5]. A moderate decrease in the oxygen concentration in the gas phase to 5 % is sufficient to activate expression of FixLJ/FixK₂-dependent targets [5]. However, in the RegSR/NifA cascade, the low-oxygen-responsive NifA protein activates the transcription of essential symbiotic nitrogen-fixation genes at an oxygen concentration at, or below, 0.5 % in the gas phase. In the present paper, the involvement of the FixLJ/FixK₂/NnrR and the RegSR/NifA cascades in the regulation of the *B. japonicum* denitrification process is reviewed.

Figure 1 Regulatory network of *B. japonicum* denitrification

Involvement of the FixJL/FixK₂/NnrR regulatory cascade

Microaerobic induction of transcriptional fusions from the *nap*, *nir*, *nor* and *nos* promoter regions to the *lacZ* reporter gene depends on the *fixLJ* and *fixK₂* genes whose products form the FixLJ/FixK₂ regulatory cascade [2,6]. FixLJ is a two-component regulatory system consisting of the haem- based sensor-kinase FixL and the FixJ response regulator. One of the known targets of FixJ in *B. japonicum* is *fixK₂*, whose product encodes the FNR (fumarase and nitrate reduction regulator)/CRP (cAMP receptor protein)-type transcriptional regulator FixK₂. Apart from being activated by FixJ-phosphate, the *fixK₂* expression is subjected to negative autoregulation [7,8] (Figure 1).

In addition to denitrification genes, other microaerobically induced targets of FixK₂ include the operon *fixNOQP* which encodes the *cbb₃* terminal oxidase that support microaerobic respiration under free-living and symbiotic conditions, operon *fixGHIS*, several haem biosynthesis genes (*hemA*, *hemB*, *hemN₁* and *hemN₂*) and some hydrogen oxidation genes (*hup* genes) [7]. FixK₂ also activates *rpoN₁* and the regulatory genes *fixK₁* and *nnrR* (Figure 1). *rpoN₁* encodes the alternative σ factor (σ^{54}) of the RNA polymerase, which acts in concert with NifA to activate gene expression. Thus RpoN₁ represents the link between the

two regulatory cascades (Figure 1). The FixK₂-activated *fixK*₁ gene encodes an oxygen-sensitive FNR-like protein that is not essential for symbiotic nitrogen fixation or for anaerobic nitrate respiration. However both processes are affected in *B. japonicum* *fixLJ*–*fixK*₂ mutants [7]. Finally, FixK₂ activates *nnrR* which encodes the FNR/CRP-type regulator NnrR [9]. Regulatory studies indicate that nitrogen oxide-mediated induction of *nap*, *nir* and *nor* genes depended on NnrR [6,9]. Thus NnrR expands the FixLJ/FixK₂ regulatory cascade by an additional control level, which integrates the nitrogen oxide signal required for maximal induction of the denitrification genes (Figure 1). Induction of the *norCBQD* promoter is completely abolished in the absence of a functional *nnrR* gene. By contrast, microaerobic induction of the *nap* or *nirK* promoters is retained in a *nnrR* mutant background, implying that the *nap* or *nirK* and the *norCBQD* promoters exhibit slight differences with regard to their dependence on FixK₂ [6,9]. In this context, recent results from our group have demonstrated that purified FixK₂ activates transcription from *nap*- or *nirK*-dependent promoters but not from *nor*-dependent promoter (E. Bueno and M.J. Delgado, unpublished work). By contrast, isothermal titration calorimetry allowed us to demonstrate that NnrR bound to a specific DNA fragment from the promoter region of the *norCBQD* genes, but not to those from the *napEDABC* and *nirK* genes. This interaction requires anaerobic conditions, but not the presence of a nitrogen oxide (E. Robles and E.J. Bedmar, unpublished work). In support of these observations, a genome-wide transcription profiling of *B. japonicum* *fixJ* and *fixK*₂ mutant strains grown under free-living microaerobic conditions has shown that *napEDABC*, *nirK* and *nnrR*, but not *norCBQD*, are the targets of the *fixK*₂ regulatory gene [4].

Involvement of the RegSR/NifA regulatory cascade

Activation of the RegSR/NifA cascade is initiated by the RegSR two-component regulatory system which induces expression of the *fixR-nifA* operon under aerobic and anaerobic conditions [10]. Transcription of *fixR-nifA* is controlled by two overlapping, but functionally distinct, promoters, *fixRp1* and *fixRp2*, that are dependent on NifA and RegSR respectively [11,12] (Figure 1). RegSR is a member of the family of two-component regulatory redox-responsive proteins present in a large number of α -proteobacteria. These proteins are named RegSR in *B. japonicum*, RegBA in *Rhodobacter capsulatus*, Rhodovulum sulfidophilum and *Roseobacter denitrificans*, PrrBA in *Rhodobacter sphaeroides*, ActSR in *Sinorhizobium meliloti* and *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*, and RoxSR in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [13]. In *Rhodobacter* species, the RegBA/PrrBA regulon encodes proteins involved in numerous energy- generating and energy-utilizing processes such as photo- synthesis, carbon fixation, nitrogen fixation, hydrogen utilization, aerobic and anaerobic respiration, denitrification, electron transport, and aerotaxis [13]. In *R. capsulatus*, the membrane-bound sensor-kinase protein RegB contains an H-box site of autophosphorylation (His²²⁵), a highly conserved quinone-binding site (the heptapeptide consensus sequence GGXXNPF which is conserved in all

known RegB homologues) and a conserved redox-active cysteine residue (Cys²⁶⁵, located in a ‘redox box’) capable of regulating the activity of RegB through forming an intermolecular disulfide bond in response to the redox state [13]. In *R. capsulatus*, the redox control of RegB probably involves both a direct inhibition of kinase activity by oxidized ubiquinone as well as an alteration of the redox state of Cys²⁶⁵ [14]. As for response regulator, RegA is a protein containing conserved domains that are typical in two-component response regulators as a phosphate-accepting aspartate residue, an ‘acid box’ containing two highly conserved aspartate residues and a helix–turn–helix DNA-binding motif [13]. Both phosphorylated and unphosphorylated forms of the cognate response regulator RegA are capable of activating or repressing a variety of genes in the regulon. In

B. japonicum, RegS possesses a highly conserved quinone-binding site and a conserved redox-active cysteine which suggests that the redox state of the membrane-localized quinone pool or the redox-active cysteine might be involved in redox-sensing. However, the precise nature of the signal that is transduced by the *B. japonicum* RegSR is unknown. RegSR is required for the aerobic and anaerobic expression of the *fixR-fixA* operon. Interestingly, a *regR* mutation reduces expression of *fixR-nifA* operon and consequently nitrogen fixation activity [10]. In contrast with RegSR, on the basis of indirect evidence, NifA was suggested to sense oxygen or redox conditions directly, probably via a metal cofactor [15]. Under micro-oxic or anoxic conditions, active NifA enhances its own synthesis via induction of the *fixRpl* promoter. In addition, it activates expression of the NifA regulon that include the *nif* and *fix* genes, which are directly involved in nitrogen fixation, and also genes that are indirectly related to nitrogen fixation or have unknown function in this process [15,16] (Figure 1). The RegSR [17] and the NifA regulons [18] of *B. japonicum* were unravelled by a genome-wide transcriptome analysis, which identified numerous new genes controlled by the RegSR/NifA cascade.

Recent results from our group show that the NifA regulatory protein is required for maximal expression of *napEDABC*, *nirK* and *norCBQD* genes, suggesting a role for RegSR/NifA regulatory cascade in the control of the denitrification process in *B. japonicum* [19]. In that study, it was shown that disruption of *nifA* caused a growth defect in *B. japonicum* cells when grown under denitrifying conditions, as well as decreased activity of Nap and Nir enzymes. Furthermore, expression of *napE-lacZ*, *nirK-lacZ* or *norC-lacZ* transcriptional fusions, as well as levels of *nirK* transcripts, were significantly reduced in the *nifA* mutant after incubation under nitrate-respiring conditions. Conversely, a *B. japonicum* *rpoN_{1/2}* mutant, lacking both copies of the gene encoding the alternative σ factor (σ^{54}), was able to grow anaerobically with nitrate as the terminal electron acceptor, and also showed wild-type levels of nitrate and nitrite reductase activities. These results suggest that the influence of NifA on denitrification genes is independent of σ^{54} [19].

Figure 2 Haem *c* staining in *B. japonicum* membranes

(A) Haem *c*-stained proteins in membranes prepared from cells of wild-type *B. japonicum* 110*spc4* (lanes 1 and 4), *regR* mutant (lane 2), *nifA* mutant (lane 3) and *fixK₂* mutant (lane 5), grown anaerobically in complete YEM medium supplemented with 10 mM KNO₃. (B) Haem *c*-stained proteins in membranes prepared from cells of wild-type *B. japonicum* 110*spc4* (lanes 1 and 3) and *regR* mutant (lanes 2 and 4), grown anaerobically in Bergersen minimum medium with butyrate (lanes 1 and 2) or succinate (lanes 3 and 4) as carbon sources and nitrate as the electron acceptor.

Haem *c* staining analyses of membranes from cells grown anaerobically in a complete medium [YEM (yeast extract/mannitol)], supplemented with nitrate, confirmed that FixK₂ is absolutely required for expression of NapC and NorC proteins (Figure 2A, lanes 4 and 5) and that maximal expression of these proteins was not reached in the *nifA* mutant (Figure 2A, lanes 1 and 3). However, in these experiments, no differences in NapC and NorC expression were observed in a *B. japonicum regR* mutant compared with the wild-type expression levels (Figure 2A, lanes 1 and 2). Supporting this observation, in microarray experiments performed to characterize the *B. japonicum* RegSR regulon, neither the *nap* nor the *nor* genes were identified as RegR-dependent genes after growth under micro-oxic conditions in complete YEM medium [17]. It might be possible that growth conditions producing redox potential variations in the cells are necessary to demonstrate the involvement of RegR on denitrification. To explore further the possibility of redox-dependent regulation of *B. japonicum* denitrification, we analysed the effect of reduced and oxidized carbon substrates on the expression of NapC and NorC denitrification proteins. Cells were grown anaerobically with nitrate as the terminal electron acceptor in a minimum medium containing a reduced carbon source, such as butyrate, or an oxidized carbon source, such as succinate. Expression levels of NorC in wild-type cells grown on succinate were significantly

higher than those observed in cells grown on butyrate (Figure 2B, lanes 1 and 3). Interestingly, when cells were grown under denitrifying conditions with succinate, there was a significant decrease in the expression of NorC in the *regR* mutant compared with the expression levels detected in the wild-type strain (Figure 2B, lanes 3 and 4). Under these growth conditions, NapC expression was not detected in the presence of either butyrate or succinate as carbon source. Under denitrifying conditions with succinate, expression of FixP, which is a 32 kDa *c*-type cytochrome associated with the cytochrome *cbb₃* complex, was significantly lower in membranes from the *regR* mutant than in those from the wild-type (Figure 2B, lanes 3 and 4). These findings confirm previous results where, by using a *fixP*'-*lacZ* fusion, *B. japonicum cbb₃* oxidase was expressed in a redox-dependent manner. Maximal expression was observed when cells were grown under denitrifying conditions in the presence of an oxidized carbon source and required the regulatory protein RegR [20]. The results shown in Figure 2(B) suggest that expression of *B. japonicum* NorC subunit of the nitric oxide reductase is under redox control and RegR is involved in this control. It is known that assimilation of reduced carbon substrates, which generate more reducing equivalents than assimilation of oxidized carbon sources, increases the reduction state of the UQ (ubiquinone) pool [21]. Under our experimental conditions, the assimilation of oxidized carbon substrates might change the redox status of the UQ pool inducing NorC expression. Alternatively, a change in the electron flow through the transport chain associated with the denitrification pathway might modulate the activity of RegSR and consequently control the expression of NorC. A similar redox-related mechanism has been proposed in *R. sphaeroides* where the activity of PrrBA depends on the electron transfer through the cytochrome *cbb₃* oxidase [22]. However, the mechanism involved in the control of *B. japonicum* denitrification by RegR is, at the moment, unknown.

In support of our results, it has been shown that PrrB/PrrA in *R. sphaeroides* and ActR in *A. tumefaciens* are involved in denitrification [23,24]. In *R. sphaeroides*, disruption of *prrA* or *prrB* causes a significant decrease in both *nirK* expression and Nir activity [24]. In *A. tumefaciens*, it has been shown that purified ActR binds to the *nirK* promoter, but not to the *nor* or *nnrR* promoters [23]. Further investigations are needed in *B. japonicum* to demonstrate the involvement of RegR on *norCBQD* gene expression and to establish whether these genes are direct, or indirect, targets of RegR.

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References

1. Delgado, M.J., Casella, S. and Bedmar, E. J. (2007) Denitrification in rhizobia-legume symbiosis. In *Biology of the Nitrogen Cycle* (Bothe, H., Ferguson, S.J. and Newton, W.E., eds), pp. 57–66, Elsevier Science, Amsterdam
2. Bedmar, E.J., Robles, E.F. and Delgado, M.J. (2005) The complete denitrification pathway of the symbiotic, nitrogen-fixing bacterium *Bradyrhizobium japonicum*. *Biochem. Soc. Trans.* **33**, 141–144
3. Bueno, E., Bedmar, E.J., Richardson, D.J. and Delgado, M.J. (2008) Role of *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* cytochrome *c₅₅₀* in nitrite and nitrate respiration. *FEMS Microbiol. Lett.* **279**, 188–194
4. Mesa, S., Hauser, F., Friberg, M., Malaguti, E., Fischer, H.M. and Hennecke, H. (2008) Comprehensive assessment of the regulons controlled by the FixLJ-FixK₂-FixK₁ cascade in *Bradyrhizobium japonicum*. *J. Bacteriol.* **190**, 6568–6579
5. Sciotti, M.A., Chanfon, A., Hennecke, H. and Fischer, H. M. (2003) Disparate oxygen responsiveness of two regulatory cascades that control expression of symbiotic genes in *Bradyrhizobium japonicum*. *J. Bacteriol.* **185**, 5639–5642
6. Robles, E.F., Sanchez, C., Bonnard, N., Delgado, M.J. and Bedmar, E.J. (2006) The *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* *napEDABC* genes are controlled by the FixLJ-FixK₂-NnrR regulatory cascade. *Biochem. Soc. Trans.* **34**, 108–110
7. Nellen-Anthamatten, D., Rossi, P., Preisig, O., Kullik, I., Babst, M., Fischer, H.M. and Hennecke, H. (1998) *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* FixK₂, a crucial distributor in the FixLJ-dependent regulatory cascade for control of genes inducible by low oxygen levels. *J. Bacteriol.* **180**, 5251–5255
8. Reutimann, L., Mesa, S. and Hennecke, H. (2010) Autoregulation of *fixK₂* gene expression in *Bradyrhizobium japonicum*. *Mol. Genet. Genomics* **284**, 25–32
9. Mesa, S., Bedmar, E.J., Chanfon, A., Hennecke, H. and Fischer, H.M. (2003) *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* NnrR, a denitrification regulator, expands the FixLJ-FixK₂ regulatory cascade. *J. Bacteriol.* **185**, 3978–3982
10. Bauer, E., Kaspar, T., Fischer, H.M. and Hennecke, H. (1998) Expression of the *fixR-nifA* operon in *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* depends on a new response regulator, RegR. *J. Bacteriol.* **180**, 3853–3863
11. Barrios, H., Fischer, H.M., Hennecke, H. and Morett, E. (1995) Overlapping promoters for two different RNA polymerase holoenzymes control *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* *nifA* expression. *J. Bacteriol.* **177**, 1760–1765
12. Barrios, H., Grande, R., Olvera, L. and Morett, E. (1998) *In vivo* genomic footprinting analysis reveals that the complex *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* *fixRnifA* promoter region is differently occupied by two distinct RNA polymerase holoenzymes. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U.S.A.* **95**, 1014–1019

13. Wu, J. and Bauer, E. (2007) RegB/RegA, a global redox-responding two-component system. In *Bacterial Signal Transduction: Network and Drug Targets* (Utsumi, R., ed.), pp. 131–148, Landes Bioscience, New York 14
14. Swem, L.R., Gong, X., Yu, C. A. and Bauer, C.E. (2006) Identification of a ubiquinone-binding site that affects autophosphorylation of the sensor kinase RegB. *J. Biol. Chem.* **281**, 6768–6775
15. Fischer, H.M., Fritsche, S., Herzog, B. and Hennecke, H. (1989) Critical spacing between two essential cysteine residues in the interdomain linker of the *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* NifA protein. *FEBS Lett.* **255**, 167–171
16. Nienaber, A., Huber, A., Gottfert, M., Hennecke, H. and Fischer, H.M. (2000) Three new NifA-regulated genes in the *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* symbiotic gene region discovered by competitive DNA–RNA hybridization. *J. Bacteriol.* **182**, 1472–1480
17. Lindemann, A., Moser, A., Pessi, G., Hauser, F., Friberg, M., Hennecke, H. and Fischer, H.M. (2007) New target genes controlled by the *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* two-component regulatory system RegSR. *J. Bacteriol.* **189**, 8928–8943
18. Hauser, F., Pessi, G., Friberg, M., Weber, C., Rusca, N., Lindemann, A., Fischer, H.M. and Hennecke, H. (2007) Dissection of the *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* NifA+ σ 54 regulon, and identification of a ferredoxin gene (*fdxN*) for symbiotic nitrogen fixation. *Mol. Genet. Genomics* **278**, 255–271
19. Bueno, E., Mesa, S., Sanchez, C., Bedmar, E.J. and Delgado, M.J. (2010) NifA is required for maximal expression of denitrification genes in *Bradyrhizobium japonicum*. *Environ. Microbiol.* **12**, 393–400
20. Bueno, E., Richardson, D.J., Bedmar, E.J. and Delgado, M.J. (2009) Expression of *Bradyrhizobium japonicum* *cbb3* terminal oxidase under denitrifying conditions is subjected to redox control. *FEMS Microbiol. Lett.* **298**, 20–28
21. Richardson, D. and Ferguson, S.J. (1992) The influence of carbon substrate on the activity of the periplasmic nitrate reductase in aerobically grown *Thiosphaera pantotropha*. *Arch. Microbiol.* **157**, 535–537
22. Kim, Y.J., Ko, I.J., Lee, J.M., Kang, H.Y., Kim, Y.M., Kaplan, S. and Oh, J.I. (2007) Dominant role of the *cbb3* oxidase in regulation of photosynthesis gene expression through the PrrBA system in *Rhodobacter sphaeroides* 2.4.1. *J. Bacteriol.* **189**, 5617–5625
23. Baek, S.H., Hartsock, A. and Shapleigh, J.P. (2008) *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* C58 uses ActR and FnrN to control *nirK* and *nor* expression. *J. Bacteriol.* **190**, 78–86
24. Laratta, W.P., Choi, P.S., Tosques, I.E. and Shapleigh, J. P. (2002) Involvement of the PrrB/PrrA two-component system in nitrite respiration in *Rhodobacter sphaeroides* 2.4.3: evidence for transcriptional regulation. *J. Bacteriol.* **184**, 3521–3529